

Web3 Services for Information Exchange in the Construction Site

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Abstract

In the AEC Industry, the repercussions of inefficient information exchange reverberate across projects, impacting timelines, budgets, and overall quality, thus, solutions to define predictable and reliable data delivery processes are needed. This research evaluates the use of Web3 services combined with Open BIM workflows for information exchange in the context of Smart Constructions. A key reference for this work is the European Project BUILDCHAIN, which aspires to create a cutting-edge marketplace that allows AEC sector actors to share their offerings, quality certificates, and credentials. In this way, this research explores advanced features such as the integration between NFT (non-fungible token) collections, DIDs (Decentralized Identifiers), and IDS (Information Delivery Specification) obtaining data from IFC Models. The execution of these integrations can offer mechanisms to support the establishment of information needs, supply the appropriate amount of data to the appropriate actors, and validate the delivery, ensuring automation and trust in the construction processes. The study will proceed in four methodological steps: (1) state-of-the-art analysis with the objective of gathering requirements and structuring the bases to generate a conceptual design for a decentralized marketplace for construction services; (2) detailed design of the solution for the specific use case, highlighting the data model of the application and the technological big picture; (3) implementation and demonstration of the Back end and Front end of the Decentralized App using React, Internet Computer Blockchain and IFC.js; (4)

usability assessment in construction practice and value added to the BUILDCHAIN. The outcome of the investigation is a web application for an NFT Marketplace where Clients can assign services to Contractors, establishing transparent requirements, and the services can be tracked through reputation systems. Therefore, the results aimed with this development are to provide more transparency for Tendering process through the decentralization of information, properly track activities linked to building life cycles, and, establish workflows for defining information requirements and ISO19650 compliance to the BUILDCHAIN use cases relying on decentralized technologies.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/vQ1-mHek2dU>

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